

Design and Modelling of a Generic Compliant Mechanism with Bi-stability and Static Balancing

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Abstract — This article presents two new compliant mechanisms that are able to achieve bi-stability and static balancing where the improved motion characteristics and reduced footprint can be obtained. One design is a single-layer symmetrical design, and the other design is a two-layer compact design. Static balancing is accomplished by adjusting the initial slope of the beam embodied in the bistable mechanism. The free-body diagram (FBD) combined with the beam constraint model (BCM) method is employed to capture the nonlinearities in the force-displacement characteristics of the proposed compliant bistable mechanism. Nonlinear Finite element analysis (FEA) is carried out to verify the modelling results.

Keywords — compliant bistable mechanism, static balancing, position-space based reconfiguration, force-displacement characteristics, nonlinear model

I. INTRODUCTION

Compliant mechanisms are of great importance in precision engineering due to their promising merits like no backlash, wear-free, smooth transition of displacement, reduced noise, etc. [1]. A wide array of applications of compliant mechanisms has been identified, for example, in the field of precise positioning [2-4], MEMS processing [5-7], and gripper design [8-10].

Due to the fact that the functionality of the compliant mechanism originates from the deformation of slender segments, they store a significant amount of energy as strain energy. This may become a significant drawback, as it causes insufficient travel range and large actuation force [11, 12]. This drawback can be subtly mitigated by the static balancing

mechanism. Bistable mechanisms are commonly utilized in the design of static balancing mechanisms [13-15]. Based on the type of motion, the existing compliant bistable mechanisms can be classified as rotational bistable mechanisms [16-18] and translational bistable mechanisms [19-22]. Tolou, et al., first introduced the idea of using two translational bistable mechanisms with different initial shapes to design a static balancing mechanism [23]. A schematic of the static balancing mechanism is shown in Fig. 1(a) [24]. By manipulating the slope of the flexure beams (α and β), the design can achieve different force-displacement characteristics. If the positive stiffness of the bistable mechanism 1 is the same magnitude as the negative stiffness of the other serially connected bistable mechanism 2, then zero stiffness can be obtained over a certain working range [24]. A schematic representation of the combination of two bistable mechanisms with different force-displacement curves is presented in Fig. 1(b). The static balancing region presented in Fig. 1(b) is the combination of two opposite stiffness. However, the design presented in Fig. 1 (a) could easily cause the open base to deflect as it is being actuated [25]. And small deflection of the base frame has a huge impact on the bistable behavior [25]. In addition, the design has an insufficient footprint. A more compact design can be created to facilitate applications where space is limited.

Designing a bistable mechanism with the aforementioned merits is a challenging task. However, we can easily generate practical and useful configurations by arranging the relative

Fig. 1. (a) A typical flexure beam arrangement in a bistable mechanism or static balancing mechanism; (b) schematic representation of the combination of two bistable mechanisms with different force-displacement curves

Fig. 2 Position-space based reconfiguration design of compliant mechanism: (a) planar symmetrical design with improved frame deformation; (b) two-layer reconfiguration with reduced footprint

positions of any two compliant joints/modules utilizing the concept of position space. This concept was firstly introduced in Ref. [26]. Using the PSR approach, compliant mechanisms can be reconfigured into various types. It is possible to use this method to change the shape and configuration of a compliant mechanism to facilitate fabrication or to improve its motion characteristics [27, 28].

To accurately model the characteristics of the proposed design, the FBD system modelling method combined with the BCM [29] was used. However, the BCM may lose certain accuracy when the synthesis beam undergoes a large axial load (normalized force beyond $[-10, 10]$). This issue can be mitigated by splitting the beam into multiple beams to extend the allowable axial force of BCM [30]. To reduce the complexity of the analytical modelling, the flexure beam embodied in the proposed bistable mechanism will be divided into two elements.

Inspired by the above discussion, we strive to design a bistable mechanism that is able to achieve static balancing by simply manipulating the slope of the flexure beams. The design also should have a reduced footprint and reduced deformation of the base frame. The nonlinear analytical formulation for such a mechanism also helps to bridge the gap in this area.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the design of the bistable mechanism. Section 3 explores the nonlinear analytical modelling of the design underlying the BCM approach and FBD. The characteristics analysis with the verification of FEA results is presented in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

II. MECHANISM DESIGN

Figure 1(a) shows a typical arrangement of flexure beams in a bistable mechanism or static balancing mechanism. By changing the position and orientation of the flexure beams, we can obtain different shapes and configurations of the bistable mechanism [26]. Figure 2(a) presents one of the configurations. The base frame in this configuration suffers both tensile forces and compressive forces imposed by the two beams at the top and two beams at the bottom, respectively. The forces of the proposed design can be canceled thus keeping the frame remain undeflected. The base frames of the design with open frames (in Fig. 1(a)) suffer only tensile forces imposed by the embodied four beams, which causes the frame to deform.

The reconfigured design in Fig. 2(a), however, has a relatively large footprint. This is achieved by positioning two beams on the second layer, where the intersection point of the beams is opposite to the one on the first layer as shown in Fig. 2(b). This is similar to folding the mechanism in Fig. 2(a) along its symmetry axis.

The complete design is mainly composed of the motion stage, base, and four flexure beams as schematically shown in Fig. 1(a). Interestingly, if we simply manipulate the slopes of flexure beams (α and β), at some point, the bistable mechanism is able to achieve zero stiffness at a certain range of motion as the concept proposed by Tolou, et al., [23]. The design in Fig. 2(a) will be further analytically modeled and simulated based on FEA software since the planar structure is handier to reconfigure and reconstruct compared to the two-layer design.

Fig. 3. Flexure beam with generalized end load

Fig. 4. The static model of half of the planar bistable mechanism: (a) half of the mechanism; (b) the FBD of the divided beams.

III. NONLINEAR ANALYTICAL MODELLING

A. Generalized flexure beam

When the BCM model [31], together with the free-body diagram (FBD), is applied to a generalized beam flexure, the nonlinear characteristics of the proposed bistable mechanism can be accurately modelled within the allowable displacement (10% of the segment length) and axial force (± 10 for the normalized axial force). As aforementioned, the flexure beam will be split into two identical elements. Each element will be synthesized by the BCM. It is necessary to solve equations associated with constitutive relationships, load-equilibrium conditions, and geometric compatibility conditions to obtain load and displacement relationships of the proposed bistable mechanism.

As shown in Fig. 3, the loading conditions for each element are represented by F_i (axial force), P_i (transverse force), and M_i (moment) acting at the tip of the beam. The resulting displacements are represented by X_i (displacement along X-axis), Y_i (displacement along Y-axis), and θ_i (rotational angle along Z-axis) with respect to the local coordinate frame. As a way to simplify the equation representation, all length parameters and translational displacements are normalized by the beam length L , forces by EI/L^2 , and moments by EI/L . Each of the normalized quantities is indicated in lower case, specifically:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i &= \frac{F_i}{EI/L^2}, p_i = \frac{P_i}{EI/L^2}, m_i = \frac{M_i}{EI/L}, x_i = \frac{X_i}{L}, \\ y_i &= \frac{Y_i}{L}, u = \frac{U}{L}, t = \frac{T}{L}, w = \frac{W}{L}, p_{oi} = \frac{P_{oi}}{EI/L^2}, \\ f_{oi} &= \frac{F_{oi}}{EI/L^2}, m_{oi} = \frac{M_{oi}}{EI/L^2}, x_{oi} = \frac{X_{oi}}{L}, y_{oi} = \frac{Y_{oi}}{L} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where I is the second moment of area of the flexure beam cross-section about the Z-axis, and E denotes young's modulus of the material. The constitutive equations of each flexure beam are represented below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_i \\ m_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & c \\ c & b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_i \\ \theta_i \end{bmatrix} + P_i \begin{bmatrix} e & h \\ h & g \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_i \\ \theta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$x_i = \frac{1}{d} p_i + \begin{bmatrix} y_i & \theta_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i & k \\ k & j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_i \\ \theta_i \end{bmatrix} + p_i \begin{bmatrix} x_i & \theta_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r & q \\ q & s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_i \\ \theta_i \end{bmatrix}$$

where the coefficients $a = 12$, $c = -6$, $d = 12/t^2$, $e = 1.2$, $g = -0.1$, $i = -0.6$, $q = -1/400$, $s = 11/6300$, and $r = 1/700$. All these coefficients are non-dimensional values that characterize a uniform flexure beam. Despite the change in beam dimensions, these numbers remain the same.

B. Kinetostatic analysis

Since the bistable mechanism is geometrically symmetrical, half of its geometry (Fig. 4(a)) is used to synthesize its kinetostatic properties. Figure 4(b) illustrates the FBD of half of the bistable mechanism, where the deformation is assumed to occur only in the flexure beam, and the other parts are rigid. And the flexure beam is divided into two identical segments to extend the allowable displacement (10% of the segment length) and axial force (± 10 for the normalized axial force) of the BCM. f_{in} is the normalized input force. f_p and m_y are the supplementary forces and moments to maintain zero rotation of the input stage.

The two flexure beams (beam I and beam II as labelled in Fig. 4) embodied in the bistable mechanism introduce 12 unknowns (3 displacement parameters and 3 force parameters for each beam). And each flexure beam has two equal elements. This introduces 24 more intermediate parameters.

Following Eq. (2), we can obtain 12 constitutive equations for the 4 elements, which are not presented here since they are generally symbolically identical.

For flexure beam I, we can derive 6 force equilibriums. It is worth noting the force equilibrium is deduced based on the deformed configuration to capture the nonlinear effect.

$$\begin{cases} p_1 = \cos \theta_2 p_{o1} + \sin \theta_2 f_{o1} \\ f_1 = \sin \theta_2 p_{o1} + \cos \theta_2 f_{o1} \\ m_1 = m_{o1} \\ p_2 = p_{o1} \\ f_2 = f_{o1} \\ m_2 = m_{o1} + f_1(x_1 + 1) - p_1 y_1 \end{cases}$$

Similar to beam I, beam II has the following load-equilibrium conditions.

$$\begin{cases} p_3 = \cos \theta_4 p_{o2} + \sin \theta_4 f_{o2} \\ f_3 = \sin \theta_4 p_{o2} + \cos \theta_4 f_{o2} \\ m_3 = m_{o2} \\ p_4 = p_{o2} \\ f_4 = f_{o2} \\ m_4 = m_{o2} + f_3(x_3 + 1) - p_3 y_3 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The geometry compatibility for each flexure beam.

$$\begin{cases} x_{o1} = x_2 - y_1 \sin \theta_2 + (1 + x_1) \cos \theta_2 - 1 \\ y_{o1} = y_1 \cos \theta_2 + y_2 + (1 + x_1) \sin \theta_2 \\ \theta_{o1} = \theta_2 + \theta_1 \\ x_{o2} = x_4 - y_3 \sin \theta_4 + (1 + x_3) \cos \theta_4 - 1 \\ y_{o2} = y_3 \cos \theta_4 + y_4 + (1 + x_3) \sin \theta_4 \\ \theta_{o2} = \theta_3 + \theta_4 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

As the flexure beams are attached to the motion stage, it yields below geometry compatibility.

$$\begin{cases} x_{o1} = y_{in} \sin \alpha \\ y_{o1} = y_{in} \cos \alpha \\ x_{o2} = y_{in} \sin \beta \\ y_{o2} = y_{in} \cos \beta \\ \theta_{o1} = \theta_{in} \\ \theta_{o2} = \theta_{in} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where y_{in} donates the input displacement. Since the motion stage only moves along Y-axis, the rotational displacement along Z-axis (θ_{in}) and the displacement in the X-axis (x_{in}) is equal to zero.

In total, 36 unknowns can be obtained numerically by solving the aforementioned 36 equations. Then, the reaction force on the motion stage can be obtained by the force equilibrium below.

$$f_{in} = 2(f_{o1} \cos \alpha + f_{o2} \cos \beta + p_{o1} \sin \alpha + p_{o2} \sin \beta) \quad (7)$$

IV. CHARACTERISTIC ANALYSIS AND FEA VERIFICATION

A study of the proposed bistable mechanism with different flexure beam slopes (α and β) was undertaken to understand how slope affects the force-displacement characteristics.

Fig. 5. FEA simulation and prototype of both planar design and two-layer design: (a) first stable position of the two-layer design, (b) its second stable position; (c) first stable position of the planar design, (d) its second stable position.

COMSOL@5.0 was used for analyzing all designs using the identical flexure beam parameters listed in Table I. Similar to the assumptions made in analytical modelling, the simulation assumes that the stages and base are rigid. Due to the large elastic deformations, nonlinear solvers were used. A finer hexahedra mesh was generated at the compliant beams to achieve accurate and stable results. The Poly(lactic acid) with Young's Modulus 3.45 GPa and Yield Strength 54.1 MPa was assigned to the material. A series of incremental displacements were applied to the input stages and the corresponding reaction forces were captured during the simulation. All parameter values have been converted back to dimensional values for a more straightforward comparison.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE FLEXURE BEAM

L	U	T
20 mm	8 mm	0.7 mm

Figure 5(a) and 5(c) plot the fixed surface and the input surface of the proposed bistable mechanisms. Figure 5(b) and (d) present the deformed configuration while giving 8 mm prescribed displacement to the motion stage. The captured maximum stress from the first stable position to the second stable position of the planar design is 42.7 MPa while the maximum stress of the two-layer design is 43.7 MPa which is smaller than the yield strength of the material. The two-layer

design is fabricated using the additive manufacturing method (3D printing). And the planar design is fabricated from a piece of Acrylic Plate using a laser cutting manufacturing approach.

The force-displacement relationship of both planar design and two-layer design with the same beam slope ($\alpha = \beta$) is plotted in Fig.6. Both FEA and analytical results indicate all the designs exhibit bistability. The FEA results of both planar design and two-layer design generally match the analytical results. The force-displacement relationship of the planar design shows a very small difference from the two-layer design. However, the two-layer design yields out-of-plane rotation which does not occur in the planar design. This drawback can be mitigated by using the three-layer design method [32]. Another pattern we can observe from Fig. 6 is that the design with a larger initial beam slope indicates a larger error. This is due to the normalised axial load applied on the elements exceeding the allowable range ± 10 . As shown in Fig. 7(a), the maximum normalised axial force for the element is 18.60 indicated by the FEA results while the analytical results showed the maximum normalised axial force is 20.21. It is possible to minimise the error between FEA and analytical results by dividing the flexure beams over two elements. This method does, however, impose a higher computational cost and difficulty in formatting the analytical model.

Figure 7(b) plots the force-displacement characteristic of the planar designs with different beam slopes ($\alpha \neq \beta$). As we

Fig. 6. Force-displacement characteristic of the planar design: (a) bistable behavior of the planar design; (b) bistable behavior of the two-layer design.

Fig. 7. (a) Normalized axial force applied on the element; (b) force-displacement characteristic of the planar designs with different beam slopes.

increase the slope of the flexure beam (β) from 5 degrees to 9 degrees, the force required to transfer between two stable positions is increased. Static balancing occurs when β reaches 9 degrees. The maximum reaction force captured by the FEA results is 0.094 N at the static balancing region. Both the FEA results and analytical results generally show the same pattern as aforementioned.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a generic compliant bistable mechanism is obtained based on the PSR reconfiguration method through which the different shapes and configurations of the bistable mechanism can be obtained. The proposed bistable mechanism is able to achieve static balancing by manipulating the slope of the flexure beams embodied in the mechanism. The two-layer design has reduced footprint and reduced base frame deflection. The BCM modelling method combined with the FBD was used to synthesize the nonlinear characteristics of the bistable mechanism. It is worth noting each flexure beam is divided into two identical elements to extend the allowable axial force of the BCM. The results show a good agreement with the FEA results for the design with a smaller beam slope (smaller axial force required to actuate and smaller motion range). It shows a larger error when the beam slope increases. Based on the discussions aforementioned, the main contribution of this paper can be summarized below:

- 1) Two bistable mechanisms that can achieve static balancing are proposed based on the PSR approach. Both the planar and two-layer designs have reduced base frame deflection compared to the traditionally arranged flexure beams (Fig. 1(a)). Typically, the two-layer design has a reduced footprint.
- 2) The nonlinear analytical modelling of the design is formulated and verified by the FEA results.

Future investigations will focus on experiment verification. The scaling down of the mechanism size provides potential application in MEMS.

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